

Xco. Previous studies used the Southern blotting technique, in which EcoRI-digested DNA was transferred to a solid support and probed with labeled DNA fragments.

The advantage of the method we used is that the relatively small number of large DNA fragments resulting from *Pst*I digestion allows RFLPs to be detected without Southern blotting. Expensive and laborious blotting, probe synthesis, hybridization, washing, and probe detection procedures are avoided.

RFLP analysis of Xco using *Pst*I involves extraction of the bacterial DNA, digestion of DNA with the restriction enzyme, gel electrophoresis, and DNA visualization. All of these procedures are done according to standard protocols. The figure shows a gel containing *Pst*I-

digested genomic DNA of selected isolates of Xco Race 2. Polymorphism is evident among the fragments that are more than 6 kilobases long.

We are using this method to examine a collection of Philippine isolates of other races of Xco. Polymorphic bands of high molecular weight have been observed for isolates of Races 2, 4, and 6.

For most of the Race 1 isolates and several Race 3 isolates, the genomic DNA was not cut by *Pst*I. DNA from these isolates can, however, be cut with other restriction enzymes.

Test DNA (from bacteriophage lambda) added to the samples can be digested by *Pst*I, indicating that the DNA of these Xco isolates is modified in a way that prevents digestion by *Pst*I. It happens that a restriction enzyme isolated

from Xco, named *Xor*I, also recognizes the sequence that is acted on by *Pst*I. This may be the reason the site is apparently modified in some strains of Xco.

The results obtained using this method of RFLP analysis are consistent in general with results of other RFLP studies for Xco, except for the undigested types seen in Races 1 and 3. In a similar study for *X. c. pv. oryzicola*, RFLPs are also revealed by digestion with *Pst*I.

Using a fast, simple method of detecting polymorphism in Xco and *X.c. pv. oryzicola* may help rice pathologists determine the population structure of these pathogens and characterize the variability among some of the races. This could help pathologists and breeders identify heterogeneous sets of strains, which can be used to develop rice varieties with broad-based resistance.

Although the method is not useful for differentiating among Race 1 and some Race 3 isolates in Philippine populations of the pathogen, it has good specificity for other races, including Race 2, currently the dominant race in the Philippines.

The relatively low effort and expense required for analysis could also make this method a useful tool in epidemiological studies. ■

Gel containing *Pst*I digested genomic DNA of selected isolate of *X.c. pv. oryzae* race 2.

A disease rating scale for screening rice genotypes for resistance to sheath blotch

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We screened 26 rice genotypes for reaction to sheath blotch (*Pyrenochaeta oryzae* Shirai ex Miyake) under artificial epiphytotic conditions.

Entries were transplanted in three 5-m-long rows each with 15 cm between plants and 20 cm between rows. At 80 d after transplanting, each plant was inoculated by inserting between the sheath and culm a one-inch-long *Typha* piece colonized with *P. oryzae*. Infected tillers, lesion length vertical spread), penetration to lower sheath (horizontal spread),

and pycnidia formation were evaluated 21 d after inoculation.

Individual parameters placed all the genotypes in extreme categories. We therefore pooled the parameters and devised a new scale.

Rating	Description
1	0-10% tillers infected; lesion length on first sheath 0-15 mm; no pycnidia formation.
2	10-20% tillers; lesion on first sheath 15-30 mm; lesion length on second sheath <20 mm; 5-10% blotch area having pycnidia.
3	20-30% tillers infected; lesion length on first sheath 30-45 mm; lesion on second sheath 20-30 mm long; 10-25% blotch area covered with pycnidia
4	30-40% tillers infected; first sheath lesion 45-60 mm long; lesion length on second and third sheaths >30 and >20 mm, respectively; 25-50% blotch area studded with pycnidia
5	>40% tillers infected; lesion length on third sheath >20 mm; specks on culm and node; 50% blotch area bearing pycnidia

Using this scale, genotypes were grouped as resistant (ratings 1 and 2), moderate (rating 3), and susceptible (ratings 4 and 5). HAU3800-1, HPU804, and RP2151-33-4 were resistant (see table). ■

Reaction of 26 rice genotypes to sheath blotch inoculation (pooled parameters). Haryana Agricultural University Rice Research Station, Kaul, India.

Reaction	Rice genotypes
Resistant (rating 1-2)	HAU3800-1, HPU804, RP2151-33-4
Moderate (rating 3)	HAU47-3780-33, HAU47-3855-1, IET7641, IET7662, IET7753, IET7758, RP2151-27-1, RP2151-140-1
Susceptible (rating 4-5)	HAU101-60, HAU101-88, HAU3855-1, HAU47-6045-1, IR13420-6-3-3-1, IR17494-32-1-1-3-3, IR19660-181-3-3-3, IR19661-23-3-2-2, IET4141, RP2151-76-1, IET7668, IET7752, RP2151-21-1, HKR101, Palman 579

Resistance of selected breeding lines to green leafhopper (GLH) and rice tungro (RTV)

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We used artificial inoculation to screen 29 breeding lines for resistance to GLH and RTV.

To screen for GLH resistance, pregerminated seeds were sown in rows in 60 × 40 × 10-cm seedboxes. Seedlings were infested with five 3d-instar nymphs/seedling 7 d after sowing and scored when susceptible check TN1 seedlings died.

To screen for RTV resistance, 10-d-old seedlings were exposed for 1 d to 2 viruliferous GLH adults/seedling (GLH had fed 3 d on RTV-infected TN1 plants). RTV infection was scored 20 d after inoculation.

Resistance to RTV was not necessarily associated with GLH resistance (see table). IR35366-62-1-2-2-3, IR45138-115-1-1-2-2, IR45136-131-2-1-1-3, IR49517-41-1-6-2-3, and IR52280-117-1-1-3 were highly resistant to GLH and RTV. IR41996-163-2-1-2, IR49455-71-3-2-3-2-2, IR50363-8-1-1-3, IR50363-61-1-2-2, and IR50376-80-1-1-2-2 were highly resistant to GLH but susceptible to RTV. IR28239-94-2-3-6-2 and IR41985-111-3-2-2-2 were susceptible to GLH but resistant to RTV. ■

Reactions of selected IR lines to GLH and RTV. Aduthurai, India.

Line	GLH damage score (SES)	RTV ^a (%)
IR28239-94-2-3-6-2	9	10 (3)
IR35366-62-1-2-2-3	3	5 (2)
IR41985-98-3-1-3-2	5	15 (4)
IR41985-111-3-2-2-2	9	25 (5)
IR41993-131-2-3-1	3	35 (6)
IR41996-12-2-2-3	7	45 (7)
IR41996-50-2-1-3	3	25 (5)
IR41996-99-1-5-2	9	40 (6)
IR41996-118-2-1-3	3	45 (7)
IR41996-163-2-1-2	1	60 (7)
IR41999-139-1-1-2-3	1	<i>b b</i>
IR42000-211-1-2-2-3	7	25 (5)
IR42068-22-3-3-1-3	0	<i>b b</i>
IR45138-115-1-1-2-2	0	5 (2)
IR45136-131-2-1-1-3	0	10 (3)
IR47761-27-1-3-6	1	60 (7)
IR49455-71-3-2-3-2-2	1	50 (7)
IR49457-33-1-2-2-2	3	40 (6)
IR49460-54-2-2-2-3	5	35 (6)
IR49492-38-2-2-2	3	45 (7)
IR49517-15-2-2-1-2-2	1	<i>b b</i>
IR49517-23-2-2-3-3	1	<i>b b</i>
IR49517-41-1-6-2-3	1	5 (2)
IR50363-8-1-1-3	1	55 (7)
IR50363-61-1-2-2	1	40 (6)
IR50376-80-1-1-2-2	3	45 (7)
IR50404-57-3-2-3	1	30 (5)
IR51009-62-3-3-3	5	15 (4)
IR52280-117-1-1-3	3	5 (2)
TN1 (susceptible check)	9	90 (9)
TKM9 (susceptible check)	<i>b</i>	85 (9)
ADT36 (susceptible check)	<i>b</i>	85 (9)

^aValues in parentheses = RTV damage rating by the Standard evaluation system for rice (SES) ^bNot tested.

New donors for green leafhopper (GLH) and rice tungro virus (RTV) resistance

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We grew more than 100 land races selected for RTV tolerance in the field from Bihar, India, on the IRRI experimental farm for seed increase in 1987 wet season. About 30 lines were completely free from visible symptoms of RTV infection.

In 1988, we screened those lines for resistance to GLH *Nephotettix virescens*

(Distant), in free-choice and no-choice tests. During 1989 dry season, six lines found to be GLH-resistant in the no-choice test were evaluated for RTV infection using artificial inoculation in the greenhouse.

Ten seedlings/earthen pot were grown in mylar cages. Viruliferous GLH nymphs fed 2-3 d on rice plants infected with rice tungro bacilliform virus (RTBV) and rice tungro spherical virus (RTSV) were released for 24 h on 2-wk-old seedlings for inoculation, at two nymphs per seedling.

Inoculated plants were kept in an insect-proof greenhouse. One month